

Pd-N-doped carbons for chemoselective hydrogenation of cinnamaldehyde: Unravelling the influence of particle size and support in multiphase batch and continuous-flow systems

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Cinnamaldehyde hydrogenation
Pd-supported nanoparticles
N-doped carbons
Multiphase systems
Continuous-flow

ABSTRACT

The chemoselective hydrogenation of the C=C bond of cinnamaldehyde (CAL) was investigated under batch and continuous flow conditions, by comparing the performance of two *ad-hoc* prepared palladium-based catalysts supported on N-doped carbons to that of a commercial Pd/C system. An impregnation (I) and a solution-mediated (S) protocols were used for the synthesis of the catalytic materials, Pd-N/C_i and Pd-N/C_s, respectively, in the presence of chitin as a precursor of the support. The S method afforded palladium nanoparticles of 2.0±0.5 nm, while by impregnation, a wider size distribution was achieved with particles mostly belonging to two groups displaying a mean radius of 3.0±0.5 nm and 8.4±0.5 nm, respectively. A parametric analysis of the hydrogenation reaction showed that both the reaction conditions and the nature of the catalysts played a role to steer the selectivity towards the formation of the desired product, 3-phenylpropanal (hydrocinnamaldehyde, HCAL). At 50 °C and 1 bar H₂, in a triphasic (liquid-liquid-liquid) batch reactor where the catalyst was compartmentalized in an ionic liquid layer, Pd-N/C_i and commercial Pd/C were almost equally active and allowed to obtain HCAL in a 90–96 % selectivity at complete conversion. On the other hand, at the same T and p (50 °C/1 bar), Pd-N/C_s was more effective in the continuous-flow mode: the process was quantitative yielding HCAL with a selectivity and a productivity of 91 % of 16 mmol (g_{cat} h)⁻¹, respectively, while the catalyst proved highly stable showing no loss of activity over 300 min of time on-stream. The reaction environment, the size and dispersion of the metal active sites, and the nature of the catalyst support were major contributors to such results, acting synergistically to each other to tune the energetics of adsorption/desorption of reactants/products, of the interfacial interactions/ barriers, and in the last analysis, of the process kinetics/selectivity.

1. Introduction

The design of safe chemical transformations is a key goal of sustainable synthesis, to which catalysis has and is largely contributing, not only by improving the selectivity towards the desired products, but also by achieving process intensification through step economy, reduced use of solvents, and more efficient work-up. This is especially true in the current scenario where the growing interest for the upgrading bio-based molecules that frequently bear multiple functionalities, makes the implementation of catalytic sequences more and more challenging [1].

A representative case is the selective hydrogenation of α,β-unsaturated carbonyls to obtain partially hydrogenated products, which are desirable intermediates for pharmaceuticals and cosmetics [2]. Albeit the hydrogenation of the C=C bond (615 kJmol⁻¹) is thermodynamically favoured over that of the carbonyl group (C=O, 715 kJmol⁻¹), the two reactions often compete. Scheme 1 exemplifies the case of cinnamaldehyde (CAL).

The process results in the formation of either cinnamyl alcohol (COL), a well-known flavouring compound, or hydrocinnamaldehyde (HCAL), an intermediate used in HIV drug production, depending on

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcata.2024.119864>

Received 9 April 2024; Received in revised form 24 June 2024; Accepted 1 July 2024

Available online 2 July 2024

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whether the carbonyl or the C=C bond is hydrogenated, respectively. However, because of the conjugated structure, the control of one process vs the other is hard so that different proportions of both the semi-hydrogenated products may be obtained. A further drawback for chemoselectivity is the subsequent formation of the fully hydrogenated derivative, hydrocinnamyl alcohol (HCOL, paths a and b). With a specific focus on the synthesis of HCAL of interest for this work, the literature reports a variety of noble metal-based catalysts, among which Pd-based heterogeneous systems have offered the best results. This behaviour has been attributed to the *d*-band electronic distribution of Pd, which is suggested to confer the metal a special capability to adsorb and activate C=C bonds. Moreover, it has been observed that the morphology and size of active sites were crucial for the products distribution, where systems characterized by smaller Pd particles tended to favour the activation/hydrogenation of C=C bonds, while larger Pd particles were more suited to the activation of C=O bonds [3]; accordingly, the most performant systems for the synthesis of HCAL were achieved using supported palladium nanoparticles (Pd-NPs) with dimensions in the range of 1.0–2.5 nm. Other fundamental aspects in the catalysts design were the nature of the support that could be responsible for strong interactions with the metal (SMSI), and the introduction of promoters in the form of other metal species as Ni, Au, and Ag.

Table S1 describes some of most significant mono- and bi-metallic systems for the conversion CAL→HCAL. A comparative analysis of Pd catalysts supported on combinations of Lanthanum dioxycarbonate (La₂O₂CO₃) and different nanomaterials as nano-rods, nanoparticles [4] and triangular-shaped nanosheets (TNS) [5] demonstrated that the TNS material substantially improved the conversion of CAL into HCAL (Table S1, entry 1). This result was attributed to the presence of surface oxygen on the La₂O₂CO₃-TNS material that exposed highly conductive (001) planes able to facilitate a charge transfer between the metal active phase and the support. This led to an increased electron density on Pd, which enhanced its performance and selectivity. Alternative Pd catalysts have been prepared by a CO-assisted reduction method which generated spherical and concave-tetrahedral Pd nanoparticles on both carbon and SiO₂ supports. (Table S1, entry 2) [6]. With the aim to control the shape and surface structure of the metal particles, this study proved that carbonaceous materials were superior to silica for the selective synthesis of HCAL, because of their hydrophobic characteristics facilitating the adsorption of the reactant CAL. A variety of other supports have been investigated including ordered mesoporous materials, such as MCM-41 and SBA-15, and porous organic frameworks [7–9]. Moreover, the use of a second metal component as iron [7], nickel [8], silver [9], and iridium [10] able to modify the electronic and/or geometric structure of Pd, has been explored to tune the selectivity of the CAL hydrogenation (Table S1, entries 3–6). The comparison of the catalytic performance of a Pd-Fe₃O₄@TPT system (TPT=hydroxyl enriched Porous-Organic-Polymer, POP) to that of a physical mixture of Pd and Fe₃O₄, demonstrated that Pd-Fe interactions on POP allowed both a quantitative conversion of CAL and full selectivity to HCAL (Table S1, entry 3) [7].

Other studies elucidated electron transfer mechanisms from Pd to other precious metals as Ir on silicon carbide supports: these processes resulted in a decreasing of the electron density in the proximity of the active sites (Pd) which favoured the adsorption of the C=C bond of CAL and its further hydrogenation (Table S1, entry 6) [10].

The presence of a second metal whether as a noble or a non-noble element, was reported to also improve the dispersion of palladium over the support. Interestingly, this phenomenon was achieved by a far more sustainable and cheaper strategy involving the use of heteroatom-doped carbonaceous supports [11,12]. An example was described by using Pd supported on oxygen functionalized graphite felts (OGFs) (Table S1, entry 7) [11]: the occurrence of strong interactions between oxygen groups on the support surface and the metal inhibited the sintering of Pd-active sites during the preparation and use of the catalyst and made it as effective – if not better – as some of the best bimetallic samples explored for the synthesis of HCAL.

This analysis highlights how not only the nature of the catalytic material *per se* but also its preparation protocol determines the economic/environmental acceptability of a given catalyst and its true potential for scalability. In the light of this, the present work has investigated two new catalytic systems for the selective hydrogenation of CAL to HCAL, which were achieved by the dispersion of palladium nanoparticles on a N-doped carbon support derived from chitin. Two approaches based on impregnation and solution methods were followed for the catalysts preparation with the aim to control the morphology and the structure of active sites, and to explore the influence of such properties on the chemoselectivity of the reaction. The performance of these catalysts, Pd-N/C_i and Pd-N/C_s, was compared to that of a commercial Pd/C used as a benchmark sample, under batch and continuous-flow (CF) mode. Results demonstrated that in the explored (batch and CF) conditions, the desired product, HCAL, was achieved with an excellent selectivity up to 96 % at complete conversion. However, beyond the size and the dispersion of the metal nanoparticles, multiple aspects were responsible for such an outcome. In the batch mode, a triphasic (liquid-liquid-liquid) system proved the most suitable configuration to steer the selectivity through an interfacial reaction where the catalyst and the reactants/product were compartmentalized in different phases. Cinnamaldehyde (CAL) hydrogenation towards (HCAL) in multiphase has been scarcely reported in literature. Only a few studies have addressed this multiphase-assisted reaction, by using a RhCl(TPPPTS)₃ aqueous solution as catalytic system [13] or by using NaBH₄ as reducing agent in a Pickering emulsion system [14]. Phase separation could influence reaction kinetics, selectivity, and catalyst segregation from reactants and products. Catalyst confinement in multiphase systems enhances downstream efficiency, enabling catalyst reuse with minimal leaching and contamination, thus improving overall process sustainability. The procedure was successful to control the products distribution, but the best catalyst was Pd/C and no appreciable advantages emerged from the use of a N-doped carbon support. In contrast, the transition from a batch to a CF process yielded notably distinct results, primarily attributed to

Scheme 1. Reaction pathways in the hydrogenation of cinnamaldehyde.

the enhanced mass transfer in continuous flow regimes. This led to increased catalytic activity across all the investigated systems compared to the outcomes observed in batch processes. In this scenario, fine-tuning the reaction selectivity was achieved through the combined effect of reaction parameters (temperature, pressure, and flow rate) and the morphological and chemical attributes of both the metal nanoparticles and the support. Catalytic hydrogenation reactions conducted under continuous-flow conditions provide substantial advantages over batch processes, thanks to the distinctive gas-liquid-solid triphasic reaction environment inherent in such transformations. Pd-N/C_s proved superior to the other tested systems: at 50 °C and 1 bar of H₂, the CF-process yielded a HCAL productivity of 16 mmol (g_{cat} h)⁻¹ with a simplified work up of the reaction mixture and product recovery. Under such (mild) conditions, Pd-N/C_s was stable for over 300 min of time-on-stream.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials and equipments

Chitin, cinnamaldehyde, EDTA, Pd(OAc)₂, isooctane, tetrahydrofuran, dioxane and isopropanol, were commercially available compounds sourced from Sigma-Aldrich. If not otherwise specified, reagents and solvents were employed without further purification. Ionic Liquid (IL) methyltrioctyl ammonium chloride ([N₈₈₈₁][Cl]) were prepared according to a method described by our research group [15]. Commercial 5 % Pd/C, 10 % Pd/C, 20 % Pd(OH)₂/C ThalesNano CatCarts® were sourced from ThalesNano. Water was MilliQ grade. H₂ (99 %) employed for batch and MP experiments was sourced from SIAD, Italy. Catalytic performances of the catalysts were evaluated in an H-Cube Mini Plus™ flow hydrogenation reactor. GC-MS (EI, 70 eV) analyses were performed on a HP5-MS capillary column (L= 30 m, Ø = 0.32 mm, film= 0.25 mm). GC (flame ionization detector; FID) analyses were performed with an Elite-624 capillary column (L= 30 m, Ø= 0.32 mm, film= 1.8 mm). All the reported reactions were run in duplicate to ensure reproducibility: unless otherwise specified, conversions and selectivity differed by less than 5 % from one test to another.

2.2. Synthesis of supported palladium nanoparticles on chitin-derived N-doped carbonaceous materials

The catalytic materials were prepared according to two synthetic strategies, namely an impregnation method (I) and a protocol in solution (S). In both cases, chitin (5 g) was employed as a precursor for the synthesis of a N-doped carbon support. Chitin was mixed with Pd(AcO)₂ (0.5 mmol) and 2-propanol (70 mL and 15 mL for the method in solution and by impregnation, respectively). EDTA (ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid, 1 g) was introduced as an additional component to favor the dispersion of the nanoparticles in the method S (solution). The suspension was stirred for 9 h at 80 °C. Then, the materials were oven dried overnight at 100 °C and subsequently pyrolyzed at 500 °C (heating rate 5 °C/min) for 1 h under N₂ atmosphere. The yield of the obtained materials was around 28±5 %.

The catalysts were labelled as Pd-N/C_i and Pd-N/C_s where i and s stands for impregnation and solution, respectively.

For continuous-flow experiments, 50 mg of each sample was loaded into ThalesNano CatCarts® (30 mm), sealed on both ends with graphite-filled PTFE sealing rings, stainless steel filters, and PTFE membranes (CatCarts® by ThalesNano Inc.).

2.3. Materials characterization

The crystalline structure of the samples prepared in this study was investigated by X-Ray Diffraction (XRD: X-Ray source of the Cu Kα radiation) by monitoring the 2θ values within 8–80° at a rate of 0.08° min⁻¹. The textural properties including surface area, pore volume and

pore size were determined from N₂ physisorption at –196 °C. The samples were outgassed at 120 °C for 2 h.

The specific surface areas, the pore volumes, and the pore size distributions were calculated/estimated by the BET method, from the adsorption isotherms, and by the Barrett, Joyner and Halenda (BJH) algorithm available as a built-in software from Micromeritics, respectively. XPS (X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy) spectra were recorded using a monochromatic X-ray Al Kα radiation. The binding energies were referenced to the C 1 s peak from adventitious carbon at 284.8 eV. High-resolution spectra were recorded by a concentric hemispherical analyser in a 29.35 eV constant energy pass, using a 200 μm diameter analysis area, and the pressure in the analysis chamber was kept below 5 × 10⁻⁶ Pa. PHI ACCESS ESCA-F V6 software was used for data acquisition and analysis. A Shirley-type background was subtracted from the signals. The spectra were analysed with Gauss-Lorentz curves for a more accurate determination of the binding energy of the atomic levels of the different elements. SEM-EDX images were acquired at an acceleration voltage of 200 kV and with a FEI Tecnai G2 system, equipped with a charge-coupling device (CCD) camera. Samples were ground and then suspended in ethanol, followed by dipping of a holey-carbon coated copper grid of 300 mesh which was left to dry under air for a few minutes prior to recording.

ICP-OES analysis was carried out to evaluate the effective Pd-loading. The samples (≈25 mg weighted in the Praxair, Sartorius, 0.01 mg) were previously inserted in Teflon vessel for acidic mineralization assisted by microwave (Ethos UP, Milestone). A mixture of 5 mL of aqua regia (3:1 HCl:HNO₃) and 2 mL of ultrapure H₂O₂ was added to the vessel, and the container was sealed and heated under microwave irradiation up to 210 °C. The solutions were then diluted with ultrapure water for the analysis. Samples were analysed with ICP-OES Perkin Elmer Optima 5300SV. Pd was quantified by means an external six-point calibration curve.

2.4. Batch hydrogenation of cinnamaldehyde

In a typical experiment, a 50 mL tubular reactor of borosilicate (Pyrex) was charged with a 0.05 M solution of CAL (5 mL, in THF, 2-ProOH or dioxane) and 50 mg of catalyst (selected between Pd-N/C_i, Pd-N/C_s or 5 % Pd/C). A 2-L rubber reservoir filled with H₂ was put on the top of the reactor to provide a static hydrogen pressure of ca. 1 bar and the reactor was kept under magnetic stirring at 50 °C for the desired reaction time (1–4 h) (a pictorial representation of the reactor is reported in the SI Section, Figure S5A). Once the catalytic test was completed, the reservoir was removed, the catalyst filtered, and the sample was analysed by GC-FID to determine both the CAL conversion and the HCAL selectivity.

2.5. Batch multiphase hydrogenation of cinnamaldehyde

In a typical experiment, a 50 mL tubular reactor of borosilicate (Pyrex) was charged with a 0.05 M solution of CAL in isooctane (5 mL), H₂O (5 mL) and [N₈₈₈₁][Cl] (500 mg) as ionic liquid. These conditions were borrowed from previous investigations of our group on the multiphase hydrogenation of different substrates [16,17]. A 2-L rubber reservoir filled with H₂ was put on the top of the reactor to provide a hydrogen pressure of ca. 1 bar and the reactor was kept under magnetic stirring at 50 °C for the desired reaction time (1–4 h) (see Figure S5B and S6). Once the catalytic test was completed, the reservoir was removed, the upper organic solution containing the reaction products was withdrawn by a syringe and analysed by GC-FID to determine the CAL conversion and HCAL selectivity.

2.6. Continuous-flow (CF) hydrogenation of cinnamaldehyde

In a typical experiment, a solution of CAL (0.05 M in 2-ProOH) was delivered to a H-Cube Mini Plus™ flow hydrogenation reactor, equipped

with different catalytic cartridges filled with the available catalysts, *i.e.* 5 % Pd/C, 10 % Pd/C, 20 % Pd(OH)₂/C, Pd-N/C_i and Pd-N/C_s, respectively. The temperature, hydrogen pressure and the flow rate were set in the range of 25–100 °C, 1–50 bar, and 0.1–0.5 mL min⁻¹, respectively. Reactions were performed for 90–100 minutes. Samples (1 mL) were collected at the reactor outlet, at regular intervals of 20 minutes and analysed by GC-FID to determine both the CAL conversion and the HCAL selectivity. The products structure was assigned by GC-MS. Characterization data are available in the SI Section, Figure S1-S3.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Catalytic materials: synthesis and characterization

Recent studies, using both experimental and computational methods, have shed light on the chemistry of nitrogen sites and their impact on the metal support interactions [18]. Among the various nitrogen species available on the surface of such supports as graphitic, pyrrolic and pyridinic nitrogen sites, the latter (pyridinic) stand out as the primary contributors to the dispersion of different metals thanks to the formation of chemical bonds with the metal nanoparticles. These interactions confer a strong resistance to metal leaching. By contrast, Coulombic repulsions between electron-rich nanoparticles and graphitic/pyrrolic nitrogen atoms (*p_z* orbital on N) promote the dispersion of the metal entities on the support.

In this scenario, commercial chitin extracted from shrimp shells biowaste is emerging as a promising source of both carbon and nitrogen for the preparation of *N*-doped carbons, that beyond the advantage of renewability/sustainability, avoids the use of noxious nitrogen-bearing chemicals as ammonia or ammonium salts. It is worth mentioning that our group has recently described the valorisation of chitin and shrimp shell wastes for the preparation of *N*-doped carbons with a high

contribution of pyridinic nitrogen [19]. As well, we have recently contributed to this subject by designing a library of catalysts comprised of nanoparticles of metal/metal oxides based on nickel, iron, cobalt and molybdenum supported on *N*-doped carbons, that proved effective for the oxidation of different primary alcohols [20].

In this study, chitin derived *N*-doped carbonaceous supports have been further investigated for the incorporation of Pd nanoparticles aimed for selective hydrogenation reactions. Fig. 1 summarises the results achieved through strategies of impregnation (I) and solution (S) (additional details are the experimental section).

Also, a commercial 5 % Pd/C sample sourced by Aldrich (lot # 14513LH-467) was used as a benchmark catalyst to explore the hydrogenation of CAL and compare the performance to that of the synthesised Pd-N/C_i and Pd-N/C_s. The Pd loading of (5 wt%) was as close as possible between the three catalysts.

TEM/SEM analyses. Method I made use of a lower volume of isopropanol (IPA) compared to method S (15 mL and 70 mL, respectively). Moreover, in method S, EDTA was introduced as an additional component. The compresence of larger amount of solvent (IPA) and a complexing agent (EDTA) acted synergically in method S by favouring a better control on the morphology and distribution of the Pd nanoparticles, which appeared smaller than in method I and more homogeneously dispersed on the carbonaceous matrix. This behaviour was corroborated by TEM analyses, displayed in Fig. 2A-B. Quasi-spherical nanoparticles were obtained for both catalytic materials. The TEM micrograph of the Pd-N/C_i sample showed palladium nanoparticles with a relatively wide size distribution, with a radius ranging from 1.0 nm to 11.0 nm, and the concomitant presence of two main particle size-distribution groups, with mean radius of 3.0±0.5 nm and 8.4±0.5 nm, respectively (Fig. 2A). By contrast, the Pd-N/C_s material exhibited a far narrower particle size distribution with a mean radius of 2.0±0.5 nm (Fig. 2B). These results are consistent with other literature reports where

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the preparation of the catalytic materials Pd-N/C_i and Pd-N/C_s by method I (impregnation, top) and method S (solution, bottom), respectively.

Fig. 2. Top: TEM images, A: Pd-N/C_i and B: Pd-N/C_s. Insets show the corresponding histograms of particle size distribution. Bottom: SEM images, C: Pd-N/C_i and D: Pd-N/C_s.

similar solution-based method (S) was described to achieve small and finely distributed metal nanoparticles of Co, Ni, Fe, and Mo on N-doped carbons, as well as the formation of single-atom catalysts [20–24]. An additional sample was prepared following the same synthetic procedure in solution but without the use of EDTA. HR-TEM micrographs of this material showed that a non-homogeneous particle distribution was achieved (See Figure S7, ESI). While there were small nanoparticles in the range of those observed for the material prepared with EDTA, the presence of agglomerates and larger-sized nanoparticles was also noted. This reinforces the idea that the use of EDTA in the solution protocol

plays an important role.

Furthermore, TEM analyses of the commercial 5 % Pd/C proved that not only the metal phase was uniformly dispersed as nanoparticles on carbon, but it displayed a narrow particle size distribution, with an average radius of 1.2 ± 0.5 nm, similar to Pd-N/C_s (Figure S8 in the SI section).

SEM images of the samples (Figs. 2C and 2D) revealed a notably rugged structure, where carbon layers appeared to overlay each other in a complex, intertwined manner. This high degree of surface roughness could be beneficial for catalytic applications by providing a larger active

Fig. 3. XRD patterns of Pd-N/C_i (A, left) and Pd-N/C_s (B, right).

surface area. The combination of rough surface textures and certain porous structure highlights the material's potential for various applications requiring active site accessibility.

XRD analyses. The XRD patterns of Pd-N/C_i and Pd-N/C_s are shown in Figs. 3A and 3B, respectively. Both materials displayed similar diffraction signals, located at ca. 25.0, 39.6, 47.0 and 68.0. The peak observed at a 2θ value around 25 was assigned to the (002) crystallographic plane characteristic of amorphous carbon with a graphene-like layered architecture, while the signals at 39.6, 47.0 and 68.0 were attributed to the crystallographic planes (111), (200) and (220) of palladium(0), typical of a face-centered cubic crystal arrangement [25]. It should be noted that even if the same signals were detected in the diffraction patterns of both samples, a critical difference in intensity and hence crystallinity resulted from the two synthetic methodologies employed in this work. The impregnation method led to sharper Pd(0)-related crystallographic peaks, associated with the presence of larger nanoparticles in the Pd-N/C_i sample, compared to the those observed in the XRD profile of Pd-N/C_s sample prepared in solution. The peak broadening was evident for all signals in Fig. 3B, while the crystallographic plane Pd(0)-(200) was only inferred from a shoulder of the peak at 39.6, corresponding to the plane (111). According to the Scherrer equation, the particle sizes for both Pd-N/C_i and Pd-N/C_s materials were determined, resulting in particle sizes of 11.6 nm and 3.7 nm, respectively. These XRD-derived particle sizes were consistent with our TEM observations.

XPS and ICP analyses. The chemical composition of the surface of the prepared catalysts was investigated by XPS. The spectra are shown in Fig. 4A-D (top) and 4E-H (bottom) for Pd-N/C_i and Pd-N/C_s, respectively. The presence of carbon, oxygen, nitrogen and palladium on the surface of both the catalytic samples was confirmed. High resolution C 1s core level spectra (Figs. 4A and 4E) were decomposed into five contributions, located at 284.3±0.2 eV, 285.7±0.2 eV, 287.2±0.2 eV, 288.6±0.2 eV and 290.0±0.2 eV, attributed to C-C/C=C bonds from graphitic and/or aromatic carbon, C-OH, C-N/C-O, C=O and CO₃²⁻ species, respectively [19]. N 1s core level spectra (Figs. 4B and 4F) showed the presence of two main contributions at 398.4±0.2 eV and 400.3±0.2 eV, which were attributed to pyridinic and pyrrolic nitrogen species, respectively. The same N-based functionalities on chitin-derived N-doped carbons were previously investigated by our group [19]: notably, these groups were claimed for a double role as: i) active sites (especially pyridinic groups) in base-catalysed reactions, such as CO₂ fixation reactions, and ii) promoters for the incorporation and dispersion

of metal nanoparticles on the carbon surface. The O 1s core level spectra (Figs. 4C and 4G) were decomposed into two contributions at 531.2±0.2 eV and 533.2±0.2 eV, which were assigned to O-metal bonds in metal oxides and to the presence of adsorbed H₂O in the catalysts structure, respectively [20]. Last and more importantly, the Pd 3d spectra XPS regions were evaluated to examine the chemical nature of palladium sites on the catalysts surface (Figs. 4D and 4H). The corresponding signals were decomposed into four contributions located at 335.1±0.2 eV, 336.2±0.2 eV, 340.3±0.2 eV and 341.5±0.2 eV. The contributions at 335.1±0.2 eV and 340.3±0.2 eV, were associated to the doublet Pd 3d_{5/2} - Pd3d_{3/2} of Pd(0) [26], respectively, while the contributions (band shoulders), located at binding energy values of 336.2±0.2 eV and 341.5±0.2 eV (associated to the doublet Pd 3d_{5/2} -Pd3d_{3/2}, respectively), indicated the presence of Pd(II) species in the form of surface palladium oxide. The discrepancy between the XPS and XRD results can be explained by the different nature and depth sensitivity of these techniques. Although XRD did not detect PdO due to its low concentration in the bulk material, the presence of oxidized palladium species was identified by XPS. These results, suggest that the synthesized nanoparticles consist primarily of Pd (0), with oxidized metal present on the surface.

Also, XPS analyses enabled us to evaluate the metal concentration on the support surface. Table 1 compares these results to the Pd-loading in the bulk determined by ICP. The latter was in agreement with the percentages (5 wt%) expected from the amounts of the precursors, both the metal salt and the chitin, employed in each methodology (I and S). Instead, from XPS, the concentration of palladium on the surface, was slightly higher, ca 7 wt%. This finding was consistent with diffusion/mass transport phenomena towards the support surface and in the bulk of the carbon material. Plausibly, during the catalyst preparation, either in the stirring of the suspension of the metal precursor and the chitin, and the pyrolysis step, the metal tended to accumulate on the surface of

Table 1
XPS binding energy values and Pd wt% according to XPS and ICP-MS results.

Sample	Pd(0) 3d _{5/2} /eV	Pd(II) 3d _{5/2} /eV	Pd loading	
			wt% by XPS	wt% by ICP
Pd-N/C _i	335.1	336.4	7.5	5.4
Pd-N/C _s	335.1	336.2	7.6	4.9

Fig. 4. XPS spectra Pd-N/C_i (top) and Pd-N/C_s (B, bottom). A: C 1s, B: N 1s, C: O 1s and D: Pd 3d XPS regions for Pd-N/C_i; E: C 1s, F: N 1s, G: O 1s and H: Pd 3d XPS regions for Pd-N/C_s.

the support regardless of the size of the nanoparticles [27–31].

N₂ physisorption analysis. Physisorption analyses did not show marked changes between the two catalysts, thereby suggesting that the textural properties of these materials were mostly affected by the precursor of the carbonaceous support (chitin). Both Pd-N/C_i and Pd-N/C_s displayed good-to-excellent features, in terms of surface area, pore diameter and pore volume, with values of ca. 402±10 m²/g, 5.9±0.5 nm and 0.19±0.05 m³/g, respectively (details on adsorption isotherms are reported in the SI section, Figure S4). Notably, these were in agreement with our previous results where a surface area of 321 m²/g was determined for metal-free N-doped carbons from chitin [19], and further corroborated the fact that the presence/incorporation of metal nanoparticles did not have a negative influence in the textural characteristics of the catalysts used in this work.

3.2. Catalytic activity

3.2.1. General

The performance of Pd-N/C_i and Pd-N/C_s for the hydrogenation of CAL were evaluated and compared to that of a commercial Pd/C sourced by Aldrich (5 wt%, lot # 14513LH-467). At least two consecutive tests were performed for any of the designed hydrogenation protocols. In all cases, values of conversion and products distribution did not differ by more than 5 % from one experiment to another, ensuring reproducibility.

3.2.2. Batch hydrogenation of CAL

Reactions were initially carried under batch conditions, using two methods, A and B, respectively (further details are in the SI section, Figures S5 and S6).

Method A (isopropanol). Method A was a traditional liquid-phase protocol, utilizing isopropanol as the solvent due to its low toxicity and solvency properties, which are well-suited for the investigated reaction [32]. Results are reported in Table 2.

Reaction conditions: CAL (0.05 M in 2-PrOH, 5 mL), catalyst (50 mg), 50 °C, 1 bar H₂. Conversion and selectivity were determined by GC.

5 % Pd/C and Pd-N/C_i allowed similar conversions at comparable times, though Pd-N/C_i proved more active in the hydrogenation of both double bonds, the C=C and the C=O, of the reactant CAL (See conversion values after 3 h, Table 2, entries 2 and 5). After 24 h, at quantitative CAL conversion, the fully hydrogenated derivative HCOL was obtained in 85 % and 62 % over 5 % Pd/C and Pd-N/C_i, respectively (entries 3 and 6). This result suggested that Pd-N/C_i exhibited slightly higher selectivity towards the hydrogenation of the C=C bonds compared to the commercial counterpart. No other products except for HCOL were detected in both cases. The absence of semi-hydrogenated product COL was consistent with path B of Scheme 1, i.e. the reaction proceeded via the complete reduction of the C=C bond followed by the C=O hydrogenation. Even so, under the conditions outlined in Table 2,

Table 2
Hydrogenation of cinnamaldehyde (CAL) over different Pd-based catalysts.

Entry	Catalyst	Time (h)	Conversion (%)	Products distribution (%)	
				HCOL	HCAL
1		1	26	69	31
2	5 % Pd/C	3	79	63	37
3		24	99	15	85
4		1	25	51	49
5	Pd-N/C _i	3	99	43	57
6		24	99	38	62
7		1	<1	99	-
8	Pd-N/C _s	3	<1	99	-
9		24	6	99	-

the two steps were not selectively achieved relative to each other. The third sample Pd-N/C_s, instead, was by far less effective: albeit the reaction showed a superior selectivity to HCOL (99 %), the conversion did not exceed 6 % even after 24 hours (entry 9).

The products distribution in the catalytic hydrogenation of cinnamaldehyde has been often reported to be structure sensitive, with larger metal particles favouring the C=O reduction [33,34]. However, given the analogy of the investigated catalysts in terms of total metal loading (approximately 5 wt%) and size of Pd nanoparticles (1–2 nm for Pd/C and Pd-N/C_s, Fig. 2 and S7), the different results of Table 2 were imputed to a combined effect of the metal particle size and dopant N species on the support. As mentioned in the introduction section, the presence of nitrogen on the carbonaceous support may result in Coulombic repulsion between the p_z orbital of graphitic nitrogen and electron-rich entities, such as nanoparticles or aromatic compounds. Keeping this in mind, an explanation for the observed results was formulated, taking into account that in the case of smaller nanoparticles, as observed in both the commercial and Pd-N/C_s samples, the higher catalytic activity of the commercial catalysts was attributed to the absence of nitrogen in the carbonaceous support, thus preventing repulsive interactions between cinnamaldehyde and the support surface. Conversely, the favourable catalytic performance observed with the Pd-N/C_i material was linked to the presence of larger nanoparticles, which could facilitate interactions between the active sites and cinnamaldehyde, circumventing the repulsive interaction with the N-doped support [35]. Nevertheless, the challenges associated with the low catalytic activity observed in the case of Pd-N/C_s samples under batch conditions were overcome by conducting the experiments under continuous flow regimes (as described in the following sections), where both selectivity and productivity were boosted. The role of the N-doping on carbon-supported metals is still controversial, but undoubtedly, it modifies the catalysts performance also by creating auxiliary catalytic centres [36].

Additional experiments were carried out by replacing isopropanol with polar non protic solvents as THF and 1,4-dioxane. Under the conditions of Table 2, in the presence of Pd-N/C_i as the catalyst, the control of selectivity was improved with HCOL reaching an 87 % selectivity at a complete conversion (see Table S2, SI section). These solvents, however, were not further investigated since their use was not recommended for their intrinsic hazard [37].

Method B (Multiphase Hydrogenation). Method B was designed using a multiphase (MP) system based on a built-in separation of reagents/products/catalyst, meaning that the catalyst was segregated in a phase different from that where the reaction took place. Such MP configurations, which have been extensively investigated by our group [16,17,38,39], have demonstrated efficient not only to improve sustainability through process intensification, but also to tune the reaction kinetics and selectivity thanks to the changes in solvation and adsorption occurring at the liquid-liquid interphases. MP-tests for the hydrogenation of CAL were performed for 1 h at 50 °C and 1 bar of H₂, in a reaction environment comprised of three immiscible liquids as water (5 mL), isooctane (5 mL), and a hydrophobic ionic liquid (IL) as methyl trioctyl ammonium chloride ([N₈₈₈₁][Cl], 500 mg). [N₈₈₈₁][Cl] was chosen for its hydrophobic properties, and the presence of water which appeared inconsequential, was necessary to ensure phase separation. Results are reported in Fig. 5 which also shows a picture of the MP-reactor with isooctane, IL and water as top, mid and bottom layer, respectively.

A striking effect of the phase separation was manifest on the reaction outcome. Experiments showed that hydrogenation of CAL was not only feasible under MP-conditions, but compared to Table 2, it proceeded much faster and with the almost exclusive formation of the desired aldehyde. In other words, at the same T and p (50 °C and 1 bar), by simply switching from an organic solvent as 2-PrOH to a MP-system, the use of 5 % Pd/C and Pd-N/C_i allowed to reach a quantitative conversion after only 1 h and most importantly, to improve the HCOL selectivity to 96 % and 90 %, respectively. The selectivity was even better (99 %)

Fig. 5. The hydrogenation of cinnamaldehyde (CAL) over Pd-based catalysts in MPs. Reaction conditions: CAL (0.05 M in isooctane, 5 mL), catalyst (50 mg), H₂O (5 mL), [N₈₈₈₁][Cl] (500 mg), 50 °C, 1 bar H₂, 1 h. Conversion and selectivity were determined by GC.

with Pd-N/C_s, though a poor conversion, <5 %, was reached, thereby paralleling the behaviour observed for this catalyst in Table 2. Albeit the confinement of C-supported metals (Pd/C, Pt/C, and Ru/C) in both organic media and in ionic liquids, was a known phenomenon, its origin is far from being elucidated [16,17]. Characterization studies of several carbons used as catalytic supports (activated carbons, carbon nanotubes, and F-doped carbons) led to conclude that their segregation in organic media was not a general behaviour. Indeed, the hydrophobic/hydrophilic properties of such materials could be tuned by acid pretreatments and were associated to the combination of surface acidity (due to carboxylic, phenolic, and lactonic groups) and the presence of Na-based impurities (0.1– 0.2 %) of the resulting carbons [38,40,41]. Different literature works also hypothesized that the embodiment/segregation observed for a variety of carbon-supported metals in ionic liquids was mostly determined by the occurrence of strong polar interactions between the dense and viscous organic liquids and the acid functionalities available on the surface of carbons [42]. In MP-reactions, ILs acted concurrently as catalyst-philic phases and as interfacial boundary layers through which the migration (adsorption/desorption) of the liquid/gaseous reagents and products to and from the catalyst, respectively, took place.

Whatever the role of the ionic liquid and the carbon support, Fig. 5 showed the impact of the multiphase conditions to enhance the reaction kinetics and selectivity. The mild operational conditions of the MP-

reaction proved further advantageous when compared to the other batch protocols described in Table S1. Moreover, from the synthetic standpoint, the catalyst segregation in the IL facilitated the separation of the product and was suited to the design of an *in-situ* catalyst recycle. This last aspect (recycle) was investigated by additional experiments carried out under the conditions of Fig. 5, except for the reaction time that was set to 45 min to moderate the final conversion and to ensure a more accurate control of the reaction outcome. Once the first reaction was complete, the upper liquid layer (containing the product) was removed from the vessel and replaced by a fresh solution of CAL in isooctane (0.05 M, 5 mL). A second reaction was then started. The recycling sequence was repeated 5 times, and the whole set of reactions was run twice to ensure reproducibility. The results are illustrated in Fig. 6.

These (recycle) tests along with results of Fig. 5 proved the robustness of the multiphase protocol not only for the selective hydrogenation of the C=C bond of CAL to obtain HCAL, but also to reuse the catalyst in a semicontinuous mode, without ever removing it from the reactor. At the same time, experiments demonstrated that the commercial catalyst, 5 % Pd/C, was comparatively equally active than Pd-N/C_i.

Another remarkable example highlighting the versatility of the multiphase approach to control the products distribution of the hydrogenation of cinnamaldehyde, was recently described by conducting the reaction in the presence of a Pt/C catalyst, in a (liquid-liquid) biphasic set-up comprised of an aqueous alkaline solution and toluene. In this case, rather than obtaining HCAL, cinnamyl alcohol was selectively achieved [43]. An interaction between the metal cation of the aq. base (KOH) and the carbonyl of the aldehyde influenced the mechanism of adsorption of the reactant on the catalyst so that the C=O bond was preferentially reduced than the C=C bond.

3.2.3. Continuous-flow (CF) hydrogenation of cinnamaldehyde

Flow chemistry has been nominated by IUPAC as one of the top ten emerging technologies for a more sustainable future [44]. Flow systems offer unique options to improve mass and heat transfers of chemical processes that become crucial to reduce the equipment size/production capacity ratio, energy consumption, and waste production [45,46]. Particularly, continuous-flow reactors are characterised by high specific interfacial areas and short molecular diffusion pathways that have proven fundamental for gas-liquid-solid triphasic reactions such as heterogeneously catalysed hydrogenation processes with gaseous hydrogen [47].

These features were considered in this study to design a continuous-flow protocol for the hydrogenation of CAL using the same catalysts explored under batch conditions, both the synthesised systems Pd-N/C_i

Fig. 6. Recycling of the A: 5 % Pd/C and B: Pd-N/C_i catalysts during the MP-hydrogenation of CAL to HCAL. Reaction conditions: CAL (0.05 M in isooctane, 5 mL), catalyst (50 mg), H₂O (5 mL), [N₈₈₈₁][Cl] (500 mg), 50 °C, 1 bar H₂, 45 min. Conversion and selectivity were determined by GC.

and Pd-N/C_s, and the commercial sample 5 % Pd/C. Experiments were carried out in a H-Cube® Mini Plus flow hydrogenation apparatus, where hydrogen gas was generated by water electrolysis and provided at the desired pressure to a liquid solution of the reactant CAL in 2-PrOH (0.05 M). Also, a blank experiment without any catalyst and an additional test in the absence of H₂ (only with Pd/C) were performed.

At the reactor outlet, aliquots of the mixture were collected and analysed by GC and GC/MS to evaluate/determine the conversion of CAL, the products distribution, and the products structure.

A screening of different reaction parameters was considered. The most representative results of these control experiments are reported in Table 3. The conversion of CAL was quantitative in all tests, and the products distribution was referred to two sets of conditions at temperature (T) and pressure (p) of 100 °C, 50 bar, and 50 °C, 1 bar, respectively. The liquid flow rate (F) was kept steady to 0.1 mL min⁻¹.

The blank experiment and the test without H₂ provided a negligible conversion, not exceeding 2 % and 6 %, respectively. These results confirmed both the need of a catalyst for the reaction and the fact solvents such as methanol, ethanol and especially isopropanol, albeit used as hydrogen donors for hydrogenation and hydrogenolysis reactions [48,49], did not play this role under the explored CF-conditions. In the presence of the commercial Pd/C, the CF-reaction of CAL could be by no means steered to the formation of the desired product of C=C bond hydrogenation HCAL. This catalyst was highly selective towards HCAL under batch multiphase conditions (Fig. 5), but, instead, it promoted the saturation of both C=C and C=O bonds of the reactant in the CF-mode: at 100 °C and 50 bar, HCOL was achieved in a 92 % amount (entry 1), and it still was the major product (85 %) even when both T and p were substantially decreased to 50 °C and 1 bar (entry 4). Within the same range of variation of the temperature and the pressure, the Pd-N/C_i sample allowed a better control of the products distribution, yielding a mixture of HCAL and HCOL in 43–60 % and 57–40 % amounts,

respectively (entries 2 and 5). Strikingly, however, was the behaviour of Pd-N/C_s: this system was substantially ineffective for batch hydrogenations, but it offered the best CF-performance with a HCAL selectivity of 52–86 % at a quantitative conversion (entries 3 and 6). The alteration in catalytic performance observed during the transition from batch to continuous flow processes is a common phenomenon in chemical synthesis. This is frequently attributed to enhanced mass and heat transfer, alongside variations in operational parameters/conditions such as flow rate, temperature, pressurization, solvent, and even the presence of impurities in the reactants' feed, all of which collectively influence the reaction environment [50,51]. Two recent studies on hydrogenation processes well exemplified the case: i) in the same paper, two different catalysts as 5 % Ni/AC and 3 % Pt/AC (AC: activated carbon) were claimed as the best options for the conversion of furfural to 2-methylfuran, the first one in the batch mode, and the second system in continuous-flow [52]; ii) a catalytic membrane composed of ultrasmall gold nanoclusters (AuNCs) and carbon nanotubes (CNTs), provided a far better kinetics for the hydrogenation of 4-nitrophenol under CF-conditions as compared to a conventional batch reactor due to a convectively enhanced mass transfer [53].

These considerations prompted us to perform a parametric analysis of the CF-reaction by selecting Pd-N/C_s as catalyst. Experiments were carried out by changing: i) T from 25 to 100 °C at constant H₂ pressure (1 bar) and flow rate (0.1 mL min⁻¹); ii) p in the range 1–50 bar of H₂ at constant temperature (100 °C) and flow rate (0.1 mL min⁻¹); and iii) the liquid flow rate (F) from 0.1 to 0.5 mL min⁻¹ at constant temperature (50 °C) and H₂ pressure (1 bar). If not otherwise indicated, the tests duration was 180 min, a period long enough to achieve stable conversion and products distribution over time. In all cases, a liquid solution of the reactant CAL in 2-PrOH (0.05 M) was used. No other products, but HCAL and HCOL were detected. Results are summarized in Fig. 7 A-C.

Temperature. At the lowest investigated pressure (1 bar) and flow

Table 3
Comparative performance of the three investigated catalysts in the CF-hydrogenation of CAL.

Entry	Cat.	T, p, F (°C, bar, mL min ⁻¹)	Products distribution, (%)	
			HCAL	HCOL
1	Pd/C	100, 50, 0.1	8	92
2	Pd-N/C _i		43	57
3	Pd-N/C _s		52	48
4	Pd/C	50, 1, 0.1	15	85
5	Pd-N/C _i		60	40
6	Pd-N/C _s		86	14

2-3 nm Pd nanoparticles

8-9 nm Pd nanoparticles

Fig. 7. Effect of a) temperature, b) H₂ pressure, and c) flow rate on the hydrogenation of CAL to COL. Reaction conditions: CAL (0.05 M in 2-PrOH), Pd-N/C_s (50 mg). Conversion and selectivity were determined by GC.

rate (0.1 mL min⁻¹), an excellent 98 % selectivity towards HCAL was achieved at 88 % conversion operating at ambient conditions (25 °C; Fig. 7A). Increasing T to 50 °C allowed a quantitative conversion, but the formation of the aldehyde decreased to 86 % and it further dropped down to 80 % and 71 % at 75 °C and 100 °C, respectively. This trend was consistent with the influence of the temperature on favoring the kinetics of both the competitive processes of hydrogenation of C=C and C=O bonds.

Pressure. At the same low flow rate of 0.1 mL min⁻¹, the effect of the pressure was investigated at a relatively high T of 100 °C to make any difference in the products distribution emerge more clearly (Fig. 7B). The most notable consequence of the increase of the hydrogen pressure from 1 to 50 bar was the decrease of the HCAL selectivity, from 71 % to 52 %, respectively, which was ascribed to a gradual larger availability of H₂ solubilized in the reaction medium (2-PrOH) and adsorbed on the catalyst. For example, at 18 °C, the mole fraction of H₂ in 1-propanol was reported to increase by a 2.4 factor if the pressure was enhanced from 13 to 30 bar [54]. The higher the amount of gas activated by the catalyst, the higher the onset of competitive hydrogenation reactions.

Flow rate. Temperature and pressure were conveniently set to 50 °C and 1 bar H₂, respectively, to continue the investigation by exploring the influence of the liquid flow rate (F, Fig. 7C). The catalytic bed tolerated a triplication of F from 0.1 to 0.3 mL min⁻¹ without any reduction in conversion, which remained quantitative. Additionally, there was a slight improvement in selectivity, rising from 86 % to 91 %. In the first instance, the result could be accounted for the lowering of the residence time (τ , from 30 to 10 min) due to the increase of F. This favoured the removal of the reactant aldehyde from the catalyst active centres in a way that the conversion was not compromised, but the predominant reaction, the C=C bond hydrogenation of CAL, became even more preferred over the competitive C=O bond process. The change of the flow rate, however, induces multiple effects also on the mixing efficiency, that are difficult to separate/distinguish experimentally from that determined by τ . It should be noted that microfluidic systems as the H-cube apparatus [55,56], generally allow a laminar flow with no turbulence or back-mixing in the reactor; though, the mass transfer of reactants is controlled not only by diffusion, but also by convection and advection that may alter the adsorption mode of the reagents on the catalyst surface and, in the last analysis, the selectivity [57,58]. The influence of F was confirmed by further increasing it up to 0.5 mL min⁻¹ ($\tau=6$ min). The reaction conversion decreased to 80 %, but HCAL was obtained as the exclusive product. Interestingly, when F was in the range of 0.3–0.5 mL min⁻¹, the overall reaction productivity was substantially steady at 17–20 mmol HCAL (g_{cat} h)⁻¹. The drop of conversion observed at the highest investigated flow rate (0.5 mL min⁻¹) was offset by the enhancement of the selectivity to 100 %.

As mentioned above and confirmed by Fig. 7, operational parameters of the continuous-flow process played a fundamental role on the superior selectivity of Pd-N/C_s; but other morphologic and electronic factors contributed to the performance of this catalyst, especially if compared to that of Pd-N/C_i. It has been proposed that because of their high

curvature, small metal particles (≤ 3 nm) do not imply steric constraints to the approach of aromatic α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds, meaning that in principle, a planar molecule as CAL can adsorb via both C=C and C=O bonds on the active centres of Pd-N/C_s (See schematic representation in Table 4) [59,60]. However, an important discriminant on the interactions between the two functional groups of CAL and the catalyst can be inferred by the electronic distribution/availability on the metal nanoparticles. Semiempirical extended Hückel calculations suggest that the chemisorption of the C=C bond on Pd is stronger than the corresponding C=O bond, due to the narrow *d*-band width of the metal [61]. Density functional theory (DFT) calculations have also been reported in the literature to examine the Wulff construction of Pd nanoparticles. The hydrogenation activity of cinnamaldehyde (CAL) for the C=C bond has been shown to depend on the shape and surface structure of Pd nanoparticles [62]. In our case, this different adsorption is likely further pronounced by the electronic alteration of Pd due to the *N*-doping of the support, to which especially small nanoparticles are expected to be sensitive. It should be noted here that for the case of oxides-supported gold catalysts, a XANES investigation demonstrated that smaller Au nanoparticles displayed an increased electron density, and the corresponding *d*-band was narrower and shifted closer to the Fermi level [63].

In this work we provide experimental evidence related to the influence of *p*-type dopants like nitrogen, which can induce more negatively charged supports, causing palladium to display more electropositive behaviour. Overall, the behaviour of Pd-N/C_s was consistent to a synergistic balance of multiple aspects (the reaction parameters, the size of the nanoparticles and the *N*-doping of the carbon support), crucial for the control of the adsorption capacity/mode and the electronic availability of the active centres, and in the last analysis, to tune the products

Table 4

Comparison of catalytic CF-methods for the selective C=C hydrogenation of HCAL.

Entry	Catalyst	Reactor	T/p (°C/bar H ₂)	Conv. (%)	HCAL, Sel (%)	Ref.
1	Pd/oCNT ^a	Fixed-bed	30/3	86	94	[65]
2	Pd/Al ₂ O ₃	Tube bundle CSM ^b	120/24	100	52	[66]
3	Pd/SiO ₂	Fixed-bed	195/100 ^e	95	80	[67]
4	Ni/TGI ^f	H-cube microreactor	100/40	80	93	[68]
5	Pd-N/C _s	H-cube microreactor	50/1	>99	91	This work

^a Oxygenated carbon nanotube (oCNT)-supported Pd nanoparticles ^b CSM: catalytic static mixer; ^c Single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWNTs) ^d High pressure millisecond reactor ^e The CF-reactor was pressurized with CO₂ (carrier/solvent), while HCO₂H was the H₂ source. ^f Ni nanoparticles on polymeric Tentagel-S-NH₂

distribution of the CF-reaction.

3.2.4. Catalyst stability over time

The cost of the catalyst in a liquid-phase reaction may represent up to one third of the total cost of the process, thereby implying how the prolonged use and stability over time of the catalyst are crucial for the assessment of a synthetic procedure [64]. This aspect was examined by conducting the hydrogenation of CAL under the conditions of Fig. 7C (50 °C, 0.3 mL min⁻¹, 1 bar H₂) for a period prolonged up to 300 min (time-on-stream, TOS). Results are illustrated in Fig. 8.

No relevant changes were noticed in the conversion of CAL and selectivity/productivity to/of HCAL which were quantitative and in the range of 86–91 % and 17–18 mmol HCAL (g_{cat} h)⁻¹, respectively, for the whole duration of the experiment, thereby demonstrating that not only Pd-N/C_s was a robust catalyst with a steady performance over time, but also the CF-protocol was reliable for the synthesis of HCAL on a lab scale and amenable of a further large-scale development. The TOF was determined under optimized reaction conditions, resulting in a value of 35 h⁻¹. While higher TOF values have been reported in recent literature [25,26], the main advantage of our protocol lies in the design of a built-in catalyst separation system for multiphase reactions or the implementation of a continuous-flow protocol. These features significantly enhance the practicality and scalability of our approach, making it suitable for potential industrial applications. Moreover, compared to some of the best CF-procedures available for the selective C=C hydrogenation of CAL (Table 4, entries 1–4), the results of Figs. 7 and 8 proved highly competitive in terms of both the synthetic outcome and operational conditions: the Pd-N/C_s catalysed reaction offered one the highest conversion/selectivity (>99 %/91 %) at a low temperature and ambient pressure (entry 5).

4. Conclusions

This paper describes the synthesis and characterization of two catalysts based on Pd supported on a N-doped carbon and compares the performance of such systems to that of a commercial Pd/C used as a benchmark sample. The study of a model reaction, the semi-hydrogenation of cinnamaldehyde (CAL) to hydrocinnamaldehyde (HCAL), has demonstrated that the investigated catalysts may offer an excellent selectivity >90 % towards the desired product, at quantitative conversion, but they display a remarkably different behaviour depending on the adopted reaction mode, in batch or flow. Experimental conditions and/or the catalyst synthesis have required a specific design. The batch reaction has been most conveniently accomplished by using Pd/C or Pd-N/C_i in a liquid multiphase system by which not only the reaction kinetics and selectivity was improved compared to a classical liquid protocol in a single solvent, but an *in-situ* recovery of the catalysts was possible for up to 5 subsequent runs without loss of performance; on the other hand, the continuous-flow reaction was successful by employing a N-doped carbon supported catalyst characterised by the presence of uniformly dispersed small Pd nanoparticles of ca. 2 nm. This catalytic system offered a stable productivity up to ca 20 mmol (g_{cat} h)⁻¹ for 300 min of time-on-stream. The control of the HCAL selectivity achieved at complete conversion, has proven consistent with the combined action of multiple aspects among which: i) for the batch reaction, the multiphase environment able to segregate the catalyst in an ionic liquid phase different from the hydrocarbon solvent where the hydrogenation took place; ii) for the CF-reaction, the process parameters as T, p, and flow rate, the size of the metal nanoparticles and the N-doping of the carbon support. These factors that contribute to the adsorption capacity/mode and the electronic availability of the metal active sites, are coherent with

Fig. 8. Catalyst stability during the CF-hydrogenation of CAL to HCAL. Reaction conditions: CAL (0.05 M in 2-PrOH), Pd-N/C_s (50 mg), 50 °C, 1 bar H₂, F (0.3 mL min⁻¹). Conversion and selectivity were determined by GC.

the mechanism and the nature of the competitive interactions of C=C and C=O bonds of aromatic α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds with small Pd nanoparticles featuring a narrow *d*-band width. Overall, nitrogen doping clearly affects the performance of catalysts with similar palladium loading and particle size, and this is further supported by the comparison with a commercial Pd/C sample.

The results of this work were comparable, if not better, to some of the best protocols available for the hydrogenation of CAL to HCAL, with additional benefits including mild operational conditions (50 °C and 1 bar of H₂), the use of one of the most common Pd-based commercial catalysts (5 % Pd/C, for the batch process), and a catalyst for the CF-reaction prepared by a simple/reproducible technique in solution that makes use of chitin as a renewable precursor for the N-doped carbon support. These advantages, so far harnessed for laboratory synthesis, pave the way for further studies and implementations on a larger scale, especially for the flow hydrogenation protocol that for its high levels of safety, control of process parameters and waste minimization, is intrinsically suited to the design of more sustainable processes.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Maurizio Selva: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Enrique Rodríguez-Castellón:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Alvise Perosa:** Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration. **Rafael Luque:** Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Daily Rodriguez-Padron:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Daniele Polidoro:** Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Tripti Chhabra:** Investigation, Formal analysis.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgments

D.R.-P. and D.P. acknowledges Oscar Trentin for his valuable contribution to this work. D.P. gratefully acknowledge Prof. R. L. for having hosted him at the chemistry department of the University of Cordoba, Spain. D.R.-P. acknowledges the project H2020-MSCA-COFUND-2019 “Global at Venice—Research and Training for Global Challenges” grant agreement No. 945361. T.C. acknowledges the European Union - Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA), for the project SusPharma grant agreement No. 101057430. This research was also funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (PID2021-126235OB-C32 funded by MCIN/ AEI/10.13039/501100011033/ and FEDER funds and TED2021-130756B-C31 MCIN/ AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by “ERDF A way of making Europe” by the European Union NextGeneration EU/PRTR). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.apcata.2024.119864](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcata.2024.119864).

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